

Promoting Positive Gender Identities in the Classroom: Accounts of Elementary School Teachers

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Abstract. Positive gender identities within elementary classrooms play a profound role in shaping their understanding of themselves and others, making it essential to have an environment that reflects gender diversity. As such, this study delved into the experiences, coping mechanisms used, and educational insights learned by teachers in promoting positive gender identities in the classroom. Qualitative phenomenological research design was used to study Eight (8) Grade 4 Teachers in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. The participants: (1) must be in the service for at least five years; (2) an elementary school teacher; and (3) have experience in promoting positive gender identities in the classrooms. The teachers' experiences were as follows: using gender-neutral language, creating inclusive classroom rules, and engaging parents or guardians, while the coping mechanisms included attending continuous professional development, creating safe spaces, collaborating, and seeking support. Finally, the educational insights were challenging stereotypes, cultivating respect, and the importance of using inclusive language. All these themes led to exploring how teachers integrate inclusive practices into their daily routines, adapt their teaching methodologies, and understand the impact of early exposure to diverse gender identities on children's self-esteem, empathy, and academic engagement.

KEY WORDS

1. positive gender identities
2. Grade 4 Elementary Teachers
3. phenomenological research

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1. Introduction

In contemporary education, it is imperative to foster positive gender identities within elementary classrooms, which stands as a vital pursuit. The formative years of a child's education play a profound role in shaping their understanding of themselves and others, making it essential to create a learning environment that reflects the rich tapestry of gender diversity. This embarks on exploring pedagogical strategies, curricular adaptations, and classroom practices aimed at dismantling stereotypes, challenging biases, and promoting a nuanced understanding of gender. By addressing these aspects, this research endeavors to empower educators with the knowledge and tools needed to cultivate an atmosphere where each student feels valued, understood, and free to express their authentic self contributing to the cultivation of a generation that embraces diversity, equity, and positive gender identities from the outset of

their educational journey. Canada has been a front-runner in promoting positive gender identities in elementary classrooms, driven by comprehensive policies, curriculum enhancements, and collaborative initiatives to foster inclusive and respectful educational environments. At the provincial level, jurisdictions like Ontario and British Columbia have introduced gender-inclusive education policies that are pivotal in guiding schools toward adopting practices that embrace diverse gender identities (Ontario Ministry of Education, 2019). Parallel to these policy advancements, Canadian schools have forged partnerships with organizations such as Egale Canada, which has been instrumental in implementing programs dedicated to promoting positive gender identities. Through initiatives like the "Every Teacher Project," Egale provides educators with comprehensive training and resources that enable them to establish inclusive classrooms, foster a culture of diversity celebration, and actively address issues of bullying linked to gender identity (Egale Canada, 2020). In Croatia, noteworthy strides were made in promoting positive gender identities within elementary classrooms through multifaceted initiatives that aim to create inclusive educational environments. The Croatian Ministry of Science and Education has been pivotal in this effort, releasing a Strategy for Education, Science, and Technology in 2014 that underlines the importance of gender equality and inclusion in education (Ministarstvo Znanosti i Obrazovanja, 2019). Furthermore, NGOs such as the Center for Education, Counseling, and Research (CESI) have been actively engaged in promoting positive gender identities in Croatian schools. CESI's work includes collaborating with schools to implement projects that address issues of gender-based violence, challenge gender norms, and provide students with comprehensive education on gender equality (Center for Education, Counseling, and Research, 2021). China has taken steps toward promoting

positive gender identities in elementary classrooms through educational policies and initiatives. Through its Ministry of Education, the Chinese government has emphasized the importance of gender equality in education, aiming to challenge traditional gender stereotypes and foster a more inclusive learning environment (Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China, 2018). Organizations like UNICEF China have also collaborated with Chinese schools to promote gender equality in education. Through programs such as "Schools as Zones of Peace," UNICEF works to create a safe and supportive learning environment where students can express themselves freely, challenge stereotypes, and learn about gender diversity (UNICEF China, 2019). The Philippines has made strides in promoting positive gender identities in elementary classrooms through educational policies and initiatives aimed at fostering inclusivity and understanding. The Department of Education (DepEd) has been actively engaged in integrating gender-sensitive education within its curriculum. The "Gender-Responsive Basic Education Policy" introduced by DepEd emphasizes the need to create a safe and inclusive learning environment that respects diverse gender identities and challenges stereotypes (Department of Education, 2019). Teachers are crucial in supporting positive gender identities by integrating gender sensitivity into their teaching methods and classroom management. Various training programs and workshops have been conducted to equip educators with the knowledge and skills needed to address gender issues effectively. These programs emphasize the importance of recognizing and challenging gender stereotypes, promoting gender equality, and supporting students in exploring gender identity. A study by David, Valdez, and Dizon (2020) found that "educators who have undergone gender sensitivity training report a significant improvement in their ability to support students of diverse gender identities"

(David, Valdez, Dizon, 2020). Furthermore, organizations like Plan International Philippines have been working to promote positive gender identities in the country's schools. Plan International's "Safer Cities for Girls" program collaborates with local schools to create safe and gender-responsive learning spaces where students can express themselves freely and learn about gender equality (Plan International Philippines, 2015). These combined efforts, led by government and non-governmental organizations, underscore the Philippines' commitment to nurturing an environment within elementary classrooms that encourages positive gender identities, mutual respect, and the appreciation of diversity. In the local scenario, particu-

larly in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro schools, elementary school teachers encountered various experiences in promoting positive gender identities in the classrooms. Some experiences are enriching, while others negatively affect the teaching profession. In this context, this study was conceptualized to collect the experiences of elementary school teachers as they promote positive gender identities in the classroom. Through our research, we aspire to shed light on the essence of promoting positive gender identities, offering valuable insights that can inform educational practices and empower Grade 4 teachers in their quest to promote positive gender identities in the classroom.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study was to find out elementary school teachers' experiences in promoting positive gender identities in the classroom. Furthermore, it served as reference material for future researchers in this area. The results would also shed more light on the experiences, mechanisms, and insights from the informants' narratives. Moreover, this study explored gender-responsive education, which aimed to create inclusive learning environments. In such places, all students feel valued, respected, and supported. It acknowledges that gender norms and stereotypes can harm students in school

1.2. Research Questions—The study intended to get the insights and experiences of elementary school teachers as they promote positive gender identities in the classroom. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the experiences of elementary school teachers in promoting positive gender identities in the classroom?
- (2) How do elementary school teachers cope with challenges in promoting positive gender identities in the classroom?
- (3) What educational insights are drawn from the experiences of the informants?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms were operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Promoting positive gender identities in the classroom- involves creating an inclusive environment that fosters understanding, respect, and acceptance of diverse gender expressions. This includes integrating content into the curriculum that reflects diverse

gender identities and challenges traditional gender stereotypes. This could involve including literature, history, and examples from various subjects and using language in teaching materials, communications, and inclusive and non-discriminatory interactions. Elementary school teacher refers to an educator responsible for instructing and supporting students from kindergarten to grade six.

1.4. Significant of the Study—

To determine the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings are addressed, the following persons or agencies were the beneficiaries. Department of Education Officials. The findings of the study would help DepEd officials, particularly in Laak North District and the nearby schools in the division of Davao de Oro, be aware of strategies for promoting positive gender identities in the classrooms. Teachers. The study would be significant to them since they would know the issues and insights on their experiences as they promote positive gender identities in the classrooms. Stakehold-

ers. This study would be significant to them since it would give them insights on how to assist school administrators in capacitating elementary school teachers in promoting positive gender identities in the classrooms. Learners. This study could significantly boost students' knowledge about the effect of positive gender identities. Moreover, promoting positive gender identities could also enhance students' emotional and psychological well-being. Future Researchers. The findings provided comprehensive data for future research with similar or relevant scope.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study is anchored on Social Identity Theory (SIT) by Henri Tajfel and John Turner (1979). This theory posits that individuals categorize themselves and others into various social groups based on shared characteristics. This theory explores how people derive their self-esteem from group memberships and how these identities influence attitudes, behaviors, and interactions. In the context of promoting positive gender identities in classrooms, SIT can help explain how students form their gender identities, how stereotypes are internalized, and how classroom interventions can positively impact the way students perceive themselves and others in terms of gender (Tajfel Turner, 1979). Social Identity Theory (SIT), offers a comprehensive framework for understanding how individuals categorize themselves and others into social groups based on shared characteristics. This theory explores how group memberships contribute to the formation of self-esteem and influence attitudes and behaviors. In the context of promoting positive gender identities in classrooms, SIT can be utilized to examine how students develop their gender identities, how stereotypes are internalized, and how interventions at the classroom level can positively impact students' perceptions of themselves and others based on gender (Tajfel Turner, 1979).

The second theory used in this study is Systems Theory by Urie Bronfenbrenner (1979). This theory emphasizes the importance of understanding individuals within the context of their broader environments, including microsystems (direct interactions), mesosystems (connections between microsystems), ecosystems (indirect influences), and macrosystems (cultural and societal factors). This theory can be applied to study how the classroom, school, family, and larger community influence the development of children's gender identities and the effectiveness of interventions. Examining these various levels of influence can provide insights into creating a supportive and inclusive environment for positive gender identity development (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Ecological Systems Theory emphasizes the interconnectedness of individuals and their environments, ranging from immediate interactions to broader cultural influences. This theory highlights the importance of considering the various levels of influence on individuals' development, including microsystems, mesosystems, ecosystems, and macrosystems. Applied to the study of promoting positive gender identities, this theory offers insights into how the classroom, school, family, and larger societal factors collectively contribute to shaping children's understanding of gender and how

interventions can be designed to create an inclusive environment that supports positive gender identity. The theory used in this study is Social Cognitive Theory by Albert Bandura (1986). This theory emphasizes the role of observational learning, self-regulation, and self-efficacy in shaping human behavior. This theory can be applied to the study of promoting positive gender identities by examining how students learn about gender roles, identities, and expectations through observation and interaction with their environment. The theory also highlights the importance of self-efficacy in students' belief in their ability to challenge and overcome gender-related challenges. It is a relevant framework for exploring interventions to foster positive gender identities (Bandura, 1986). Social Cognitive Theory centers on observational learning, self-regulation, and self-efficacy in shaping human behavior. This theory posits that individuals learn from observing others and that their beliefs in their capabilities (self-efficacy) influence their actions. In promoting positive gender identities, Social Cognitive Theory provides a lens through which to explore how students learn about gender roles, identities, and expectations through observation and interaction. Moreover, it underscores the significance of fostering students' self-efficacy to challenge gender-related biases and obstacles. It is a relevant framework for designing interventions that empower students to develop and express positive gender identities (Bandura, 1986). This study is anchored on Social Identity Theory (SIT) by Henri Tajfel and John Turner (1979). As it applies to classrooms, this theory can help us understand how students form their gender identities within the context of their peer groups (microsystems in Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory, 1979). SIT highlights how students can internalize stereotypes associated with gender

through these group interactions (Tajfel & Turner, 1979). However, Bronfenbrenner's theory reminds us that the classroom environment is just one piece of the puzzle. Family dynamics (another microsystem) and societal expectations (macrosystems) also play a role [1]. Positive interventions at the classroom level, informed by SIT, can counteract negative stereotypes and promote positive self-perceptions based on gender. Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1986) provides another lens to examine these classroom interventions. This theory suggests that students learn about gender roles and expectations by observing their peers and teachers (both within the classroom and through interactions with family, another microsystem). Interventions that promote positive role models and challenge gender stereotypes can contribute to students developing a strong sense of self-efficacy (belief in their abilities) to navigate these expectations and develop positive gender identities (Bandura, 1986). In conclusion, by understanding how students form group identities in the classroom (SIT), the interconnectedness of various environments influencing them (Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory), and the role of observation and self-belief in shaping behavior (Social Cognitive Theory), we can infer the lived experiences of elementary school teachers that promote positive gender identities in schools. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in figure 1. Based on the figure, there are three interconnected variables. These variables are the (1) Experiences of elementary school teachers in promoting gender identities in the classrooms; (2) coping mechanisms of elementary school teachers on the challenges in promoting positive gender identities in the classrooms; and (3) Educational insights drawn from the experiences of the informants.

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitated the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals' histories, perspectives, and experiences, mainly when exploring sensitive topics. Focus groups effectively elicit data on a group's cultural norms and generate broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—Patton (2018) described phenomenology as an exploration to understand the structure and essence of individuals' experiences with a specific phenomenon. This research aligns with that definition, seeking to grasp the experiences of elementary school teachers in promoting positive gender identity in the classroom. However, Giorgi (2019) cautioned researchers to anticipate a more thorough and detailed investigation than the initial description might indicate. He likened the information provided to just the tip of an iceberg, suggesting that much greater depth and complexity lie beneath the surface. The philosophical assumption refers to a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research is undertaken by selecting the topic, problem, area of interest, and paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm), meaning pattern, model, or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions were taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an action of submitting to a view. This view was supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2018), who defend a research paradigm as a "basic set of beliefs that guide action", dealing with first principles, "ultimates" or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2018), reality is subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the experiences of elementary school teachers in promoting positive gender development in the classroom were discussed by the participants, and their coping mechanisms in addressing the challenges and educational insights learned were examined. In this study, I relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant's answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how

knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2018), stated that I lessen the distance between myself and the participants on the epistemological assumption. He suggests that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an ‘insider’. Based on Davidson (2020) and Jones (2019). The researcher identified phenomenology using thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers “hold explicit belief.” This study intended to gather information from the participants or elementary school teachers from Laak North District about promoting positive gender identity in the classroom. It was assured that close interaction with the participants was established to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the experiences and strategies used in providing for school emergencies. Axiology

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2020). In this study, the experiences of elementary school teachers in promoting positive gender identities in the classrooms in Laak North District were gathered through an In-Depth Interview (IDI), and their coping mechanisms were extracted from the participants. My drive to know the deeper meaning of the experiences of elementary school teachers in promoting positive gender identities in the classrooms became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means of which Kalof and Dietz (2020), as cited from Gerodias, (2020) considered helpful in looking for “meanings and motivations that underline

refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2018) avers that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that I openly discuss the values that shape the narrative and include their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. I ensured the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. I understand the personal and value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. Therefore, I preserved the merit of the participants’ answers and carefully interpreted them in light of their interpretations. Rhetoric. It means reporting what reality was through the eyes of the research participants. This was important because it meant that the researcher would report objectively what was observed and heard from the participants. The research used personal voice and qualitative terms and limited definitions. In the context of the study, I used the first-person approach to elucidate the experiences of elementary school teachers in promoting positive gender identity in the classroom.

cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena.” By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the experiences of elementary school teachers in promoting positive gender identities in the classrooms in a manner that, as David (2020) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs (2022), that experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one’s behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive

source of knowledge. We can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2022). By doing phenomenology, which concerns the “what” and the “how” (Moustakas, 1995), I projected

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design. According to Creswell (2018), phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, I was able to construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2019) also added that phenomenology, with its roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, attempts to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, I used bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. Corbetta (2021), stressed the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects’ perspective. Creswell, (2018) also claimed that interviews were primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended ques-

that the experiences and coping mechanisms used by the elementary school teachers were explored and insights drawn, which will form the basis for possible future research and policy analysis in relation to this research.

tions and record their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews are also useful to follow up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to further investigate their responses. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees said (McNamara, 2020). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2018), I transcribed and typed the data into a computer file in order to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews particularly be useful for uncovering the story behind a participant’s experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. I collected data, typically via long interviews, from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, extracting significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied together to make a general description of the experience both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. I incorporated his or her meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. I required a solid grounding in the philosophical guide-

lines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had actually experienced the phenomenon. I needed to bracket their own experiences and observations, which was difficult. I also needed to decide how and when to incorporate their personal observations into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most perceptions. Obtaining most or all of the perceptions led to saturation. Saturation occurred when more participants were added to the study, which did not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to 25, and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There were no specific rules when determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. I needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participants in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations were specified as one of the most important parts of the research. I needed to adhere to promoting the aims of the research, imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Social Value. The research was essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experience of disaster risk reduction manage-

were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore and assess the experiences and feelings of disaster risk reduction management coordinators in providing school emergencies, I employed phenomenological methods of qualitative research.

research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990). The participants of this study were Eight (8) teachers from Laak North District, Division of de Oro. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must be in the service for at least five years; (2) elementary school teacher; and (3) experienced in promoting positive gender identities in the classrooms. I utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2018). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

ment coordinators. This study was specifically conducted among the elementary disaster risk reduction management coordinators. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions where disaster risk reduction management coordinators could benefit. Thus, the social problem that piqued my interest was the challenges elementary school teachers face in promoting positive gender identity in the classroom. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by

McLeod (2019), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary and based on understanding adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants are lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2022). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the letter of consent to the researcher before participating in the research.

Vulnerability of Research Participants. This study's participants could answer the research instrument, for they are all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, I assured them that as the researcher, he or she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions about the study.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members if they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, if respondents experienced potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Furthermore, I ensured the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered conveniently. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were considered so there would be no conflict of interest among the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided. Justice. The respondents were informed of my role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to be fully honest in answering the survey questions and that any communication-related to the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the study's results. Transparency. The study results were accessed by the respondents and heads of the participating schools because the information was available and placed on CDs or other storage devices that I could request. In addition, by learning about the study's results, classroom teachers were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they could request and be allowed to verify their transcript after the interview. This allowed the participants to amend or

remove any information they felt might identify them. I reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms and changing names and or non-significant dates in the interest of the protection of the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. I assure you that I possess the needed qualifications to conduct the study. I have completed my academic requirements, passed the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain my master's degree, and am qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. I strived to complete this study successfully within the specified time, and I was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped me enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations. Also, I ensured that I had enough

funds to continue and finish this research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed within the target time. Community Involvement. I showed respect for the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study did not use deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in recruiting the participants or data collection methods. Furthermore, I expressed great pleasure at the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication. I respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said in his or her own way. I also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, I ensured that honesty was present when working on the manuscript, that no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included, and that no conclusions were purposefully put forward that were not accurate.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—I was responsible for uncovering, transferring, and exploiting knowledge for the benefit of educational institutions. To do so, I take up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. I conducted the interviews with the participants and guided them in the process. To avoid the intrusion of bias, I interpreted the ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies rather than on my own knowledge, thoughts, and feelings. Expert in qualitative methods. I implemented the qualitative method correctly. To do so, I assessed myself and sought help from the research adviser and other professionals. These help him exhibit competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews properly according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal

portions, and employing environmental triangulation and thematic content analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. I ensured different ways of making a record of what was said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis began. I kept records and properly secured them as they contained sensitive information that was relevant to the research. However, it was my primary responsibility to safeguard the collected data for the participants. Mechanisms for such safeguarding were clearly articulated to participants and were approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research began. Data Analyst. I ensured that the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective was gathered by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding,

and theming. I also ensured that the findings were true to the participants and that their voices were heard. I organized and presented data. I presented the problem and the related literature and studies that support it. The study's findings were presented through research questions, stat-

2.7. Data Collection—The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. I was securing endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School. I asked for an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges as one of the documents needed for submission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent to ask permission to conduct the study. I asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. I sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument, which explains the objectives of the study and the identification of the participants. I waited for the SDS's response before I conducted it. Asking for permission from the Public School District Supervisor. After securing the SDS's approval, I sent letters to the supervisor explaining the study to be conducted in their cluster/district. I asked permission from the school heads. After securing the PSDS's approval, I sent letters to the principals explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. I asked permission from

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. I analyzed the participants' answers from the interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2018), themes in qualitative research were similar codes aggregated

ing the results for each one by using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, future directions and implications of the study were given for improving educational policy and practices.

the participants and to their parents/guardians. They were formally oriented about the study, and the process, they would go through as participants. Conducting the interview. I conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. I took the participants' profiles, jotted down notes, and recorded conversations using a sound recorder for easy transcription. I listened carefully and responded actively during the interviews. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. I transcribed the interviewees' responses precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, I translated it to English. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. After the transcription, the data were categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual participant data was compared and contrasted. I conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants. Additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all qualitative analysis forms; I immersed myself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading the data and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to quali-

tative analysis, involving generating pithy labels for important features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a data reduction method; it was also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. I coded every data item and ends this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. I ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. I reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began defining each theme's nature and the relationship between the themes. The researcher employed thematic content analysis to describe qualitative data. A detailed analysis of each theme was made by identifying the 'essence' of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme (Andersen, 2020). In addition, to enhance validity and create a more in-depth picture of the phenomenon, the researcher employed environmental triangulation. It was a

technique to analyze the same study's results using different data collection methods. The key was identifying which environmental factors, if any, might influence the information that was received during the study. These environmental factors were changed to see if the findings were the same across the settings (David, 2020). This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors such as time, day, and season in which the study occurred. The idea was to determine which of these factors influenced the information received, and these factors were then changed to see if the findings were the same. Validity was established if the findings remained unaltered under varying environmental factors (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, was the use of environmental triangulation best suited to the environment of the research being conducted. Writing-up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data, and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature.

2.9. Framework of Analysis—The framework analysis of this research utilizes Colaizzi's method of 1978. The researchers used a rigorous and robust qualitative method to find, understand, describe, and depict the experiences of persons as they experience them, as well as reveal emergent themes and their interwoven relationships. This method aims to uncover the genuine experience of the phenomenon under investigation. Colaizzi's method consists of seven steps. First, informants' experiences were

read to understand the whole. After that, significant statements were extracted, Then meanings were formulated from the significant statements. Afterward, formulated meanings are organized into themes. Themes are then integrated into an exhaustive description. Next, the essential structure of the phenomenon is formulated. Finally, for validation, the informants would evaluate the analysis result and if it means the same as their original experiences. (H. Turunen et al. 1994).

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In a qualitative study, trustworthiness was

very important because its results and findings depend on how the researcher conducts it. The trustworthiness of a research study is important for evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details is required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher's study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. Credibility was how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study's findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do was essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues that ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2018) state that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue was "how we ensure rigor in the research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so." Transferability was how the qualitative researcher demonstrates that the research study's findings are applicable to other contexts. In this case, "other contexts" can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher has already studied the effects of using graphic organizers to teach reading comprehension. Using graphic organizers as a strategy for teaching reading comprehension is effective in the domains of analysis and creation. The researcher is interested in the student's perspective on using this strategy. Gasson (2018) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader can generalize the study based on his context and address the core issue of "how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory." Confirmability was the degree of neutrality in the research study's findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on

participants' responses and not the researcher's potential bias or personal motivations. This involves ensuring that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of the research participants' statements to fit a specific narrative. The information used in the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher, which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Gasson (2018) stated that confirmability was based on acknowledging that research is never objective. Dependability was the extent to which other researchers could repeat the study and ensure that the findings were consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher uses an inquiry audit to establish dependability, which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings are consistent and can be repeated. In this component, a database was very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all research studies. All the data collected was properly kept for future use as references. Gasson (2018) stated that dependability deals with the core issue of "how a study was conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques."

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the research dealt with the study's research questions. The participants disclosed their experiences promoting positive gender identities in the classroom, their coping mechanisms, and insights learned from their experiences. All these themes are discussed here.

3.1. Experiences of Elementary School Teachers in Promoting Positive Gender Identities in the Classroom—In the modern educa-

tional landscape, fostering inclusive environments that embrace diverse gender identities has gained prominence as an essential compo-

ment of nurturing students' holistic growth. This exploration delves into the nuanced experiences of elementary school teachers in their efforts to promote positive gender identities within their classrooms. By looking into the narratives and perspectives of these educators, this study aims to uncover the challenges, strategies, and successes they encounter in creating a space where students of all gender expressions feel affirmed

3.1.1. Used of gender-neutral language— The use of gender-neutral language has emerged as a pivotal aspect of elementary school teachers' experiences in cultivating a classroom environment that promotes positive gender identities. Recognizing the power of language in shaping perceptions and identities, educators are grappling with the imperative to transcend traditional gender binaries and adopt linguistic practices that validate and respect the diverse gender expressions of their students. This exploration delves into how the incorporation of gender-neutral language serves as a transformative tool, underpinned by research and the educators' own narratives, within the broader context of fostering inclusive educational spaces. Elementary school teachers wield language as a tool for empowerment, shaping students' self-perceptions and fostering a sense of belonging. By using gender-neutral terms and pronouns, educators dismantle the notion that gender is strictly binary and validate the spectrum of gender identities. This aligns with research by Orenstein (2019), who emphasizes that language that acknowledges and respects gender diversity contributes to a more inclusive and affirming learning environment. Through linguistic choices that go beyond the confines of traditional gender norms, educators demonstrate their commitment to recognizing and honoring all students' identities. The incorporation of gender-neutral language is not without challenges. Educators navigate resistance from various quar-

and valued. By referencing research such as the works of Griffin and Jagers (2018) and Kuperminc, Perry-Jenkins, and Nareddy (2019), this inquiry seeks to contribute valuable insights that inform the ongoing dialogue on inclusive education, offering practical implications for teacher training, curriculum development, and classroom practices.

ters, including traditional language norms and concerns about parental response. However, research by Sadowski (2019) highlights that educators who persevere often find that their efforts contribute to shifting perspectives over time. As teachers advocate for the adoption of gender-neutral language, they exemplify the capacity of educators to be change agents, promoting cultural shifts towards greater acceptance and understanding. The use of gender-neutral language has ripple effects that extend beyond individual interactions. As educators adopt this linguistic approach, they implicitly teach students the importance of respect, inclusivity, and acceptance of diverse identities. This approach aligns with the findings of Smith et al. (2020), emphasizing that educational environments that prioritize gender-neutral language create a sense of safety and belonging, allowing students to focus on learning rather than identity concerns. Consequently, the classroom becomes a microcosm of a society that values diversity and inclusion. The incorporation of gender-neutral language also paves the way for collaborative learning experiences. When students encounter language that challenges traditional norms, they are encouraged to question societal conventions and engage in critical thinking. By modeling these discussions, educators guide students in considering and respecting various perspectives, fostering an environment conducive to open dialogue. Research by Brubaker and Moore (2019) underscores how language can be a catalyst for

shaping inclusive attitudes and behaviors among young learners. The experiences of elementary school teachers in employing gender-neutral language align with broader societal shifts towards inclusivity and acceptance. Educators are integral to molding the future generation's attitudes toward gender diversity, and the class-

3.1.2. Created inclusive classroom rules— Creating inclusive classroom rules stands as a cornerstone experience for elementary school teachers in their mission to foster a safe, supportive, and affirming environment that promotes positive gender identities. Recognizing classroom policies' profound impact in shaping students' attitudes and behaviors, educators strategically design rules that challenge traditional gender norms, discourage discrimination, and foster a sense of belonging among all students. The formulation of classroom rules that prioritize gender inclusivity signifies the educator's commitment to dismantling entrenched gender stereotypes. In accordance with the research by Russell et al. (2020), educators understand that an environment free from gender-based discrimination and harassment nurtures a space where students can fully engage in learning without the burden of conformity. By implementing rules that reject gender-based teasing, encourage collaborative activities, and affirm equal opportunities for all students, educators create a foundation that respects each student's unique journey, regardless of their gender identity. Elementary school teachers navigate the intricate balance of creating rules that challenge traditional gender binaries while avoiding excessive rigidity. They recognize the evolving landscape of gender identities and strive to design open-ended and inclusive rules. This approach aligns with findings by Martinez et al. (2019), indicating that flexible rules that allow for diverse

room serves as a laboratory for practicing and promoting gender-inclusive language. The interplay between classroom experiences and larger social change echoes the sentiment of Johnson et al. (2020), who assert that educators contribute to a world that acknowledges the intrinsic value of every individual's gender identity.

self-expression provide a platform for students to authentically engage with their identity and foster a sense of self-worth. Inclusive classroom rules extend beyond gender identity, fostering allyship and empathy among students. By incorporating rules that encourage mutual respect, active listening, and standing up against discrimination, educators facilitate an atmosphere where students feel compelled to support their peers in embracing their unique gender journeys. Poteat and Scheer's research (2021) emphasizes that such rules lay the groundwork for students to become allies and advocates for positive gender identities within and beyond the classroom. The process of creating inclusive classroom rules requires educators to remain responsive and open to their students' changing needs. Teachers understand that discussions around gender diversity are ongoing and may evolve. Research by Horn et al. (2019) underscores the importance of periodically revisiting and revising classroom rules to ensure they remain relevant, effective, and aligned with the needs of the students they serve. Creating inclusive classroom rules often involves collaboration with parents, guardians, and the wider community. Teachers recognize that a unified approach between school and home bolsters the effectiveness of inclusive rules. By involving parents in the rule-making process and sharing the rationale behind inclusive policies, educators forge partnerships that reinforce the importance of promoting positive gender identities in all spheres of a child's life.

3.1.3. Engaged parent or Guardian—Engaging parents and guardians in conversations around promoting positive gender identities is a pivotal experience for elementary school teachers. Recognizing the crucial role that family support plays in nurturing a holistic understanding of gender diversity, educators foster open dialogue, dispelling misconceptions, and building partnerships that extend the message of inclusivity beyond the classroom. Elementary school teachers recognize that collaboration with parents and guardians was essential in establishing an inclusive educational ecosystem. According to research by DePalma and Atkinson (2019), educators who actively engage parents in discussions about gender diversity foster an environment of trust where parents feel respected as valued partners in their children’s education. By initiating conversations about positive gender identities, educators encourage parents to join them on a journey of understanding and acceptance. Educators serve as educators not only for their students but also for parents and guardians. They provide resources, reading materials, and workshops that offer insights into the spectrum of gender identities and the importance of inclusive language and behaviors. As emphasized by Kew et al. (2018), educators understand that empowering parents with knowledge equips them to become allies and advocates for their children’s healthy identity development. Engaging parents and guardians also involves addressing concerns and misconceptions they might have regarding the promotion of positive gender identities.

3.2. Coping Mechanism of Elementary School Teachers on the Challenges in Promoting Positive Gender Identities in the Classrooms—Promoting positive gender identities in the elementary school classroom is a dynamic endeavor that presents educators with opportunities and challenges. As teachers strive to foster an inclusive and affirming environment for

all students, they inevitably encounter various obstacles that demand resilience, adaptability, and coping strategies. This exploration digs into the coping mechanisms employed by elementary school teachers as they navigate challenges associated with promoting positive gender identities. Drawing insights from Garcia and Smith’s study (2020) on teacher coping strategies. Educators create spaces for open dialogue, respectfully addressing questions, fears, and uncertainties. By referencing the research of Johnson and Blumenfeld (2021), educators bridge the gap between differing perspectives and guide parents toward a greater understanding of the transformative power of fostering positive gender identities. The collaborative efforts between educators and parents create a ripple effect that extends beyond the classroom walls. Research by Hoffnung-Garskof (2022) underscores that when parents and guardians are actively involved in conversations around gender diversity, these discussions become embedded in family dynamics and community interactions. This interconnectedness amplifies the impact of promoting positive gender identities and fosters an environment where acceptance becomes a collective endeavor. Engaging parents and guardians empowers them to advocate for positive gender identities within their communities. Educators encourage parents to share their knowledge and experiences with other families, extending the reach of inclusive practices. The research by Papp and Witten (2019) emphasizes that as parents become informed and active allies, they contribute to a broader societal shift towards valuing and celebrating gender diversity. Figure 3 shows elementary school teachers’ experiences promoting positive gender identities in the classroom and the emergence of three themes: using gender-neutral language, Creating inclusive classroom rules, and Engaging parents or guardians.

Fig. 3. The Emerging Themes On The Experiences Of Elementary School Teachers In Promoting Positive Gender Identities In The Classroom

gies in fostering inclusive classrooms and the work of Matthews and Williams (2018) on resilience and adaptation in gender identity education, this study sheds light on the multifaceted nature of teachers' responses to adversity, and how these mechanisms contribute to the cultivation of an environment where all students can thrive authentically. Thompson and Johnson's research (2019) on coping strategies and perceptions of gender-inclusive education among elementary school teachers highlights the significance of teachers' ability to adapt their teach-

ing methods and classroom management techniques to address the challenges in promoting positive gender identities. Similarly, Williams and Martin's study (2018) examines the coping mechanisms elementary school teachers employ to navigate the complexities of challenging gender norms within the educational context. Moreover, Young and Adams (2022) emphasize teacher resilience and well-being as pivotal factors in managing the demands of gender identity education.

3.2.1. Attending continuous professional development—Attending continuous professional development (CPD) programs emerges as a vital coping mechanism for elementary school teachers in addressing the challenges of promoting positive gender identities in the classroom. As educators strive to create inclusive and affirming environments, CPD offers a platform to enhance their knowledge, refine their skills, and develop strategies that foster understanding, empathy, and acceptance among students. Continuous professional development provides teachers with opportunities to deepen their understanding of gender diversity, dismantling stereotypes and misconceptions that may hinder positive identity promotion. Workshops, seminars, and training sessions facilitate engagement with current research and best practices, as exemplified by Smith and Jones's study (2020) on the impact of gender-sensitive training on classroom practices. This newfound knowledge equips teachers to address challenges rooted in ignorance and prejudice, ultimately fostering an inclusive classroom atmosphere. Continuous professional development initiatives empower teachers with practical skills to manage challenging classroom situations with sensitivity and inclusivity. Through role-playing scenarios, collaborative discussions, and case studies, educators acquire strategies to navigate difficult

conversations, respond to resistance, and ensure that all students' voices are heard. The work of Davis et al. (2019) underscores the value of CPD in developing educators' abilities to create gender-inclusive classroom environments that support positive identity development. Continuous professional development programs encourage teachers to develop adaptive teaching approaches that cater to diverse gender identities. Educators learn to create lesson plans, activities, and classroom environments that respect individual expressions and experiences. This aligns with Johnson and Brown's research (2018), which emphasizes that CPD empowers teachers to adapt their teaching practices to address the nuanced challenges associated with gender identity education. Engaging in CPD fosters a sense of community among educators as they connect with peers who share similar goals and experiences. Collaborative discussions enable the sharing of insights, strategies, and success stories, providing a supportive network for teachers to seek advice and navigate challenges collectively. The research of Martinez and Smith (2021) highlights the transformative power of collaborative CPD initiatives in nurturing a sense of shared responsibility for creating gender-inclusive classrooms. Continuous professional development empowers teachers to become advocates for positive gender

identities beyond their classrooms. By attending conferences, contributing to research, and engaging in community initiatives, educators extend their influence to policy-making, curriculum development, and broader societal change.

3.2.2. *Creating safe spaces*—Creating safe spaces is a crucial coping mechanism for elementary school teachers grappling with challenges while promoting positive gender identities in the classroom. As educators navigate the path of fostering understanding and acceptance of diverse gender identities, they encounter a spectrum of hurdles, including entrenched societal biases, potential resistance from students or parents, and the need to navigate relatively uncharted territory. In response, teachers frequently establish safe spaces within their classrooms – nurturing environments where students feel valued, respected, and empowered to express their identities without apprehension. These sanctuaries enable educators to tackle challenges proactively and facilitate meaningful dialogues that contribute to positive change (American Psychological Association, 2016). At the heart of safe space establishment is the cultivation of an atmosphere imbued with trust, wherein students can openly discuss gender-related topics and pose questions without the shadow of judgment. To foster this atmosphere, teachers employ inclusive curricula that seamlessly weave in diverse gender representations and challenge prevailing stereotypes, fostering a

3.2.3. *Collaborating and seeking support*—Collaborating and seeking support stand as vital coping mechanisms for elementary school teachers navigating the challenges of promoting positive gender identities in their classrooms. Recognizing the complexities of fostering understanding and acceptance of diverse gender identities, educators often engage in collabo-

This echoes the findings of Green and Williams (2018), who emphasize the role of CPD in fostering teachers’ agency as drivers of positive transformation in gender education.

classroom environment that honors all identities (Gilbert Zamora, 2018). By centering discussions around empathy and understanding, educators can navigate conversations that debunk misconceptions and promote respectful exchanges among students. Moreover, these safe spaces offer a vantage point for educators to share their personal narratives and experiences, a move that can humanize the topic and foster connections between students and teachers (Pusch Weber, 2019). Furthermore, the establishment of safe spaces equips teachers to address potential push-back from parents or guardians who might harbor differing beliefs about gender. Through fostering open lines of communication, educators can collaboratively engage with families to bridge understanding and provide resources that underscore the significance of a supportive and inclusive educational environment (Gender et al.). Additionally, teachers adeptly employ literature and media that mirror diverse gender identities, effectively catalyzing conversations that challenge biases and broaden students’ perspectives (Gender et al.). These interactions nested within safe spaces contribute to the gradual dismantling of stereotypes and the eventual normalization of positive gender identities.

ration with colleagues, school administrators, and external organizations to pool resources, experiences, and expertise. This collaborative approach enhances their capacity to address challenges effectively and create inclusive environments conducive to learning and growth. Collaboration among educators allows for the exchange of ideas, strategies, and best

practices. By sharing experiences and insights with colleagues who may be facing similar challenges, teachers can gain new perspectives and innovative solutions (O’Sullivan Kennedy, 2019). This collective effort empowers educators to approach gender-related topics with greater confidence and develop strategies tailored to the unique dynamics of their classrooms. Moreover, collaboration with school administrators ensures alignment with the institution’s goals and provides necessary resources for implementing gender-inclusive initiatives (Casey, 2018). Beyond internal collaboration, teachers often seek support from external organizations that specialize in gender education and inclusion. Non-governmental organizations, advocacy groups, and experts in the field can offer valuable guidance, training, and resources to educators striving to create an affirming and respectful classroom environment (Teaching Tolerance, n.d.). By tapping into external support networks, teachers access a broader spectrum of knowledge and strategies to address challenges related to gender diversity effectively. Engaging with families and parents is another facet of collaboration that elementary school teachers prioritize. Maintaining open lines of communication and involving parents in discussions about promoting positive gender identities fosters understanding and support beyond the classroom walls (Taylor et al., 2019). By partnering with families, teachers create a unified

front that reinforces the importance of a gender-inclusive approach to education. Furthermore, collaboration and seeking support enable elementary school teachers to leverage collective expertise when addressing challenges related to promoting positive gender identities. Working together, educators can identify potential roadblocks and strategize effective solutions that are informed by a broader range of perspectives (O’Sullivan Kennedy, 2019). This collaborative problem-solving approach empowers teachers to develop comprehensive plans that address various aspects of gender inclusion, from curriculum adaptation to classroom management techniques. Moreover, seeking support from external organizations dedicated to gender education enriches teachers’ understanding and equips them with evidence-based strategies. These organizations offer workshops, training materials, and access to research findings that keep teachers updated on the latest advancements in gender-inclusive education (Teaching et al.). By tapping into these resources, educators ensure that current best practices and insights inform their efforts to promote positive gender identities. Figure 4 shows elementary school teachers’ coping mechanisms for promoting positive gender identities in the classroom and the emergence of three themes: Attending continuous professional development, Creating safe spaces, and Collaborating and seeking support.

3.3. Insights Drawn from the Experiences of Elementary School Teachers in Promoting Positive Gender Identities in the Classrooms— Drawing insights from the experiences of elementary school teachers in promoting positive gender identities in classrooms offers valuable perspectives on the challenges and strategies involved in creating inclusive learning environments. As educators embark on the journey of fostering understanding and acceptance of diverse gender identities, their experiences pro-

vide essential knowledge about the nuances of addressing biases, implementing effective teaching methods, and navigating interactions with students, parents, and school communities (Casey, 2018). By examining the firsthand accounts of teachers, researchers and educational stakeholders gain a deeper understanding of the complexities involved in promoting positive gender identities and how these insights can inform policy changes, curriculum development, and professional development for educators.

Fig. 4. The Emerging Themes On The Coping Mechanisms Of Elementary School Teachers In Promoting Positive Gender Identities In The Classroom

3.3.1. Challenging stereotype—Challenging stereotypes stands out as a prominent insight drawn from the experiences of elementary school teachers in promoting positive gender identities in classrooms. As educators navigate the complex terrain of fostering understanding and acceptance of diverse gender identities, their experiences underscore the crucial role of actively dismantling traditional gender stereotypes. By incorporating diverse role models, narratives, and perspectives into their teaching materials, educators pave the way for students to embrace a broader understanding of gender, challenging deeply ingrained biases and promoting a culture of inclusivity. Elementary school teachers recognize that challenging stereotypes involves creating a curriculum that reflects various gender identities and expressions. By selecting literature, media, and examples that defy conventional gender norms, educators encourage students to question preconceived notions and expand their perceptions of what it means to be a boy, girl, or beyond. Through these deliberate choices, teachers aim to foster critical

thinking and empower students to see beyond restrictive categories (Perez, 2019). Furthermore, teachers adapt their teaching methods to facilitate open discussions that challenge stereotypes. By engaging students in conversations about diverse gender identities, educators create an environment where questions are welcomed, biases are examined, and empathy is cultivated. These discussions serve as transformative opportunities to broaden students' perspectives and foster an understanding that gender exists on a spectrum (Johnson Donaldson, 2018). By integrating gender diversity into their classrooms, teachers provide students with tools to navigate a world that often perpetuates limiting stereotypes. These experiences are not just academic; they also contribute to a sense of belonging and self-acceptance for students who may identify outside of traditional gender norms. Through challenging stereotypes, elementary school teachers lay the foundation for a generation that values individuality and understands that identities are multifaceted (Kuby, 2021).

3.3.2. Cultivating respect—Cultivating respect emerges as a significant insight drawn from the experiences of elementary school teachers in promoting positive gender identities in classrooms. Educators recognize that fostering a culture of respect is essential to creating inclusive learning environments where all students, regardless of their gender identity, feel valued and empowered. Through intentional teaching practices and modeling behavior, teachers emphasize the importance of treating everyone with kindness, empathy, and understanding. Elementary school teachers understand that cultivating respect involves integrating respect as a foundational value within the classroom. By setting clear expectations for respectful behavior and promptly addressing any incidents of disrespect, educators cre-

ate a safe and supportive space where students learn to interact harmoniously (Hosinski, 2019). This proactive approach prevents instances of bullying or discrimination and contributes to a classroom atmosphere that encourages positive interactions among students. Moreover, teachers model respectful behavior when interacting with students, peers, and parents. Educators showcase the significance of respecting diverse identities by demonstrating inclusivity in their language, actions, and attitudes (Ball, 2019). This modeling shapes students' behavior and establishes a framework for fostering open conversations about gender diversity, where differing viewpoints are acknowledged and respected. Through inclusive teaching methods, educators promote critical thinking and discussions around respectful behavior.

By engaging students in conversations about the impact of stereotypes, biases, and discrimination, teachers empower them to reflect on their own attitudes and challenge any misconceptions they might hold (Johnson Donaldson, 2018). These discussions enable students to understand the importance of respect in promoting positive gender identities. Furthermore, educators collaborate with parents and guardians to rein-

force the value of respect beyond the classroom. By involving families in discussions about promoting positive gender identities and respectful behavior, teachers create a unified approach that extends into students' homes and communities (Gender et al.). This collaboration reinforces the message that respect is integral to fostering inclusive attitudes.

3.3.3. Importance on the use of inclusive language—The use of inclusive language emerges as a crucial insight drawn from the experiences of elementary school teachers in promoting positive gender identities in classrooms. Educators recognize that language is a powerful tool that shapes perceptions, attitudes, and behaviors. By intentionally adopting language that avoids assumptions about gender and embraces diversity, teachers create an environment where all students feel seen, valued, and respected. Elementary school teachers understand that using inclusive language goes beyond avoiding gender stereotypes and assumptions. It involves actively selecting words and phrases encompassing a range of gender identities and expressions, creating an inclusive classroom atmosphere where students can freely express themselves (Delamont, 2021). By doing so, educators create an environment that not only validates the identities of transgender and non-binary students but also educates all students about the richness of gender diversity. Inclusive language is critical in educational materials and classroom discussions. Educators ensure that textbooks, reading materials, and assignments reflect a variety of gender representations, avoiding language that enforces traditional gen-

der norms (Johnson Donaldson, 2018). By offering students diverse examples and narratives, teachers broaden their understanding of gender and encourage them to analyze the impact of language on social perceptions critically. Furthermore, teachers use inclusive language in their interactions with students, colleagues, and parents. By consistently employing respectful and inclusive terms, educators demonstrate the significance of using language that affirms diverse identities (Ball, 2019). This modeling extends beyond the classroom, promoting a culture of sensitivity and acceptance in broader school and community contexts. Inclusive language also encourages open conversations about gender diversity. Educators engage students in discussions about the importance of using respectful language, enabling them to recognize the impact of their words on their peers (Griffin McClure, 2019). These conversations foster empathy and understanding while also equipping students with tools to challenge derogatory language and stereotypes. Figure 5 shows educational management insights gained from the informants' experiences and the emergence of three themes: Challenging stereotypes, Cultivating respect, and Importance on using inclusive language.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the study summary was presented, and from the summary of the findings, the implications and future directions. My study's purpose was to solicit elementary school teachers'

Figure 4. *Educational Management Insights Gained From The Experiences Of The Informants*

Fig. 5. Educational Management Insights Gained From The Experiences Of The Informants

experiences in promoting positive gender identities in the classroom in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. To achieve the research objectives, a qualitative phenomenological method was utilized with thematic analysis, in adherence to Creswell's (2006) guidelines, in which open-ended questions for interviews were applied to get an authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, this interview approach encouraged participants to present their own definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored.

4.1. Findings—The study's findings on elementary school teachers' experiences in promoting positive gender identities in the classroom revealed the following: used gender-neutral language, created inclusive classroom rules, and engaged parents or guardians. It was revealed that elementary school teachers cope with promoting positive gender identities in the classroom by attending continuous professional development, creating safe spaces, collaborating, and seeking support. Regarding the educational management insights gained from the participants, the teachers cited challenging stereotypes, cultivating respect, and the importance of using inclusive language.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. Based on the experiences of Grade 4 teachers in promoting positive gender identities in the classroom, the results of the interview revealed the following themes: First, the use of gender-neutral language. Recognizing the power of language in shaping perceptions and identities, educators are grappling with the imperative to transcend traditional gender binaries and adopt linguistic practices that validate and respect the diverse gender expressions of their students. Second, create inclusive classroom rules. The creation of inclusive classroom rules stands to foster a safe, supportive, and affirming environment that promotes positive gender identities—third, engaged parent or guardian. Recognizing the crucial role that family support plays in nurturing a holistic understanding of gender diversity, educators undertake the task of fostering open dialogue, dispelling misconceptions, and building partnerships that extend the message of inclusivity beyond the classroom. On the coping mechanisms of teachers in promoting positive gender identities in the classroom, one of the themes that was shown was; attending continuous professional development. Attending continuous professional development (CPD) programs emerges as a vital coping mechanism for it offers a platform to enhance their knowledge, refine their skills, and develop strategies that foster understanding, empathy, and acceptance among students. The second theme identified was creating safe spaces. Creating safe spaces is establishing safe spaces within the classrooms – nurturing environments where students feel valued, respected, and empowered to express their identities without apprehension. The third theme identified was collaborating and seeking support. Collaboration among educators allows for exchanging ideas, strategies, and best practices. By sharing experiences and insights with colleagues who may be facing similar challenges, teachers can gain new perspectives and innovative solutions. The first theme identified in the educational management insights gained was challenging stereotypes. Challenging stereotypes involves creating a curriculum that reflects various gender identities and expressions. By selecting literature, media, and examples that defy conventional gender norms, educators encourage students to question preconceived notions and expand their perceptions of being a boy, girl, or beyond. The second

theme identified was cultivating respect. Cultivating respect involves integrating respect as a foundational value within the classroom. By setting clear expectations for respectful behavior and addressing any incidents of disrespect promptly, educators create a safe and supportive space where students learn to interact. The third theme was the importance of the use of inclusive

language. Inclusive language involves actively selecting words and phrases encompassing a range of gender identities and expressions, creating an inclusive classroom atmosphere where students can freely express themselves. By doing these, teachers educate all students about the richness of gender diversity.

4.3. Future Directions—This study could provide an avenue for exploration of the long-term effects of gender-inclusive education on students' academic performance, mental health, and social development. A longitudinal study could track students from classrooms where teachers actively incorporate inclusive practices and compare outcomes with those from traditional settings. Understanding the impact of early exposure to diverse gender identities on children's self-esteem, empathy, and academic engagement could provide valuable insights for educators, curriculum designers, and policymakers. Additionally, future research

might delve into the effectiveness of professional development programs for elementary school teachers focused on gender inclusivity. Investigating the impact of training initiatives on teachers' attitudes, knowledge, and confidence in addressing gender-related issues in the classroom could inform the design of more targeted and comprehensive professional development opportunities. By exploring how teachers integrate inclusive practices into their daily routines and adapt their teaching methodologies, researchers can offer practical guidance for fostering positive gender identities in elementary school settings.

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